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J. Chem. Phys. 163, 164509 (2025)

<https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0292952>

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Cite as: J. Chem. Phys. 163, 164509 (2025); doi: 10.1063/5.0292952

Submitted: 24 July 2025 • Accepted: 2 October 2025 •

Published Online: 27 October 2025

View Online

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Note: This paper is part of the Special Topic, Mesoscale Fluid Dynamics.

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ABSTRACT

It is experimentally well-established that non-equilibrium long-range correlations of concentration fluctuations appear in free diffusion of a solute in a solvent, but it remains unknown how such correlations are established dynamically. We address this problem in a model of Donev, Fai, and Vanden-Eijnden (DFV), obtained from the high-Schmidt limit of the Landau–Lifshitz fluctuating hydrodynamic equations for a binary mixture. We consider an initial planar interface of the mean concentration field in an infinite space domain, idealizing prior experiments. Using methods borrowed from turbulence theory, we show both analytically and numerically that a quasi-steady regime with self-similar time decay of concentration correlations appears at long time. In addition to the expected “giant concentration fluctuations” with correlations $\propto r$ for $r \lesssim L(t) = (Dt)^{1/2}$, with diffusivity D , a new regime with spatial decay $\propto 1/r$ appears for $r \gtrsim L(t)$. The quasi-steady regime arises from an initial stage of transient growth $\propto t$, confirming the prediction of DFV for $r \gtrsim L(t)$ and discovering an analogous result for $r \lesssim L(t)$. Our results give new insight into the emergence of non-equilibrium long-range correlations and provide novel predictions that may be investigated experimentally.

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I. INTRODUCTION

One of the important discoveries in the statistical physics of the late 20th century was the generic spatial long-range correlations in non-equilibrium steady-states, first predicted theoretically^{1–5} and subsequently confirmed in laboratory experiments.^{6,7} Such non-equilibrium long-range correlations have been observed experimentally even in transient regimes, notably in the free diffusion of an initial blob of solute in a liquid solution.^{8–12} These so-called “giant concentration fluctuations” (GCFs) were successfully explained by linearized fluctuating hydrodynamics,¹³ patterned after the earlier theoretical study on non-equilibrium steady-states.⁵ In low-gravity experiments without quenching by buoyancy effects, these GCFs have been observed to propagate even up to the system size, on the order of centimeters.^{14,15} Many questions remain open in this area, both theoretically and experimentally, and are the subject of

intensive ongoing investigations.^{16,17} One general fundamental question is the dynamical emergence of such long-range non-equilibrium correlations,^{18–20} which is the subject of the present paper for the particular case of concentration fluctuations in free liquid diffusion.

Our study is based on the remarkable theory of Donev, Fai, and Vanden-Eijnden (DFV),²¹ which revealed a close analogy between the emergence of GCFs in free liquid diffusion and the cascade of a passive scalar advected by a turbulent velocity field. More precisely, DFV considered nonlinear fluctuating hydrodynamics for the concentration field advected by the thermal fluctuating velocity field in the high Schmidt-number limit, $Sc = \nu/D \gg 1$, a condition that holds rather generally for liquid mixtures. Because the velocity dynamics associated with kinematic viscosity ν are very fast in this limit compared with the dynamics of the concentration associated with diffusivity D , the fluctuating hydrodynamic equation for the

latter reduces to a version of the *Kraichnan model* of a turbulent scalar, in which the advecting velocity is Gaussian and white-in-time.^{22,23} Building upon earlier, more heuristic theory,²⁴ DFV showed that the observed macroscopic diffusivity D of the concentration emerges as an “eddy-diffusivity” renormalizing the bare diffusivity D_0 predicted by kinetic theory and satisfying the Stokes–Einstein relation $D = k_B T / 6\pi\eta\sigma$, with η the shear viscosity of the solvent and σ the molecular radius of a solute molecule. Exploiting their high-Schmidt limiting theory both theoretically and numerically, DFV predicted that in free diffusion of a blob of mean concentration with initial gradient $|\nabla c_0|$, the long-range non-equilibrium correlations in the scalar structure function $S(\mathbf{k}, t)$ emerge dynamically through a “cascade process,” with an initial short-time regime for which $S(\mathbf{k}, t) \sim \frac{k_B T}{\eta} |\nabla c_0|^2 t k^{-2}$. The long-time behavior in a quasi-steady regime expected both by experiments^{8,15,17} and linearized fluctuating hydrodynamics¹³ has $S(\mathbf{k}, t) \sim \frac{k_B T}{D\eta} |\nabla \bar{c}(t)|^2 k^{-4}$, but the numerical dependence on wavenumber observed by DFV seemed closer to k^{-3} . This disagreement was rather perplexing because Donev and his collaborators had previously obtained the expected quasi-steady result numerically both with direct simulation Monte Carlo^{25,26} and also with nonlinear fluctuating hydrodynamics not simplified by the high-Schmidt limit.^{27,28} In fact, an overdamped approximation extremely closely related to the DFV model succeeded in reproducing numerically the theoretically expected result¹⁸ as well.

Recently, this discrepancy has been removed by two of us,²⁹ who showed analytically that the DFV theory does indeed yield the expected quasi-steady result in free diffusive mixing. Those authors hypothesized that the original numerical simulation of DFV had too short a scale range to exhibit a clear power-law so that the fitting interval for a k^{-4} law was uncertain. To our knowledge, this scaling has not yet been observed numerically in the DFV model and, most importantly, it is not understood how the long-range non-equilibrium correlations arise dynamically in free diffusion. To address both of these questions, we consider here the simplest example²⁹ with an initial concentration profile

$$c_0(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{c_0}{2} \left(1 + \operatorname{erf} \left(\frac{z}{2\sqrt{D\tau}} \right) \right), \quad (1)$$

in infinite three-dimensional Euclidean space, which is inhomogeneous only in the z -direction. The parameter τ with units of time is introduced to set the magnitude of the initial concentration gradient as $|\nabla c_0| = c_0 / \sqrt{4\pi D\tau}$. Physically, the profile (1) can be obtained as the solution of the usual macroscopic diffusion equation with diffusivity D , starting from an initial Heaviside step-function profile at a “virtual time” origin $-\tau$. We determine in this example precisely how long-range non-equilibrium concentration correlations emerge in free diffusion by applying novel theoretical and computational methods for the DFV model borrowed from the problem of turbulent scalar advection.^{22,23} The growth of non-equilibrium concentration fluctuations seems not to have been studied before in free diffusion, although previous studies^{18,19} have investigated this problem instead in a transient thermodiffusion process, both through experiments and numerical computations. The results of these prior studies will be compared below with our own analytical and numerical results.

II. QUICK REVIEW OF DFV THEORY

Prior to presenting our new methods and results, we briefly review the DFV theory and the computational schemes they developed. By means of a multiple-scale asymptotic method, DFV (and also Ref. 30, Appendix B) showed that the nonlinear fluctuating hydrodynamic equation for the concentration field in the high-Schmidt limit reduces to the Stratonovich stochastic equation

$$\partial_t c = -\mathbf{w} \odot \nabla c + D_0 \Delta c, \quad (2)$$

where the thermal velocity field \mathbf{w} is no longer obtained from a dynamical equation but instead is a Gaussian random field with mean zero and prescribed covariance

$$\langle \mathbf{w}(\mathbf{x}, t) \otimes \mathbf{w}(\mathbf{x}', t') \rangle = \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') \delta(t - t'), \quad (3)$$

where in terms of the Greens function \mathbf{G} of the Stokes operator,

$$\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') = \frac{2k_B T}{\eta} (\boldsymbol{\sigma} * \mathbf{G} * \boldsymbol{\sigma}^\top)(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}'). \quad (4)$$

Following DFV, we have introduced into the spatial covariance of \mathbf{w} a low-pass filtering operator $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$, which smoothly removes wavenumbers $>1/\sigma$. In fact, nonlinear fluctuating hydrodynamic equations such as (2) are generally understood to be “effective field theories” with an explicit high-wavenumber cutoff,^{31–33} and all of the parameters in the model depend upon that cutoff. With wavenumber cutoff $\sim 1/\sigma$, the parameter D_0 has the meaning of “bare diffusivity” of the solute. Note that we have omitted a molecular noise term in Eq. (2) proportional to $\sqrt{D_0}$ and in fluctuation–dissipation balance with the diffusion term $D_0 \Delta c$ [see Ref. 21, Eq. (4) or Ref. 30, Eq. (12)]. As already emphasized by DFV, that noise term is negligible for the non-equilibrium phenomena of interest and, in fact, the diffusion term proportional to the bare parameter D_0 can generally be dropped as well.

To solve the stochastic equation Eq. (2), DFV developed two different algorithms. One approach was an Eulerian numerical scheme, with a staggered finite-volume space discretization and, in particular, a strictly non-dissipative discretization of the advection term. The velocity realizations were obtained by solving the steady Stokes equation with a stochastic forcing term representing thermal noise by means of an iterative Krylov linear solver. This approach maintains a discrete fluctuation–dissipation balance but requires a small, non-vanishing $D_0 > 0$ to dissipate structures finer than the grid created by advection. In this case, the bare diffusion term is discretized by a stable, implicit method such as Crank–Nicolson. The time-stepping was performed by an Euler–Heun predictor–corrector scheme, which is weakly first-order accurate. This high-Schmidt reduction was found to be more efficient by a factor proportional to Sc compared with the numerical solution of the full non-linear fluctuating hydrodynamic equations, which requires solving an extra dynamical equation for the fluctuating velocity field and time-resolving the fast viscous dynamics.

The second numerical method developed by DFV was a Lagrangian approach to solve Eq. (2) with $D_0 = 0$, which represents the solution with initial data c_0 by the method of characteristics as

$$c(\mathbf{x}, t) = c_0(\boldsymbol{\xi}(\mathbf{x}, 0)), \quad (5)$$

where $\xi(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is the Lagrangian flow map that satisfies the Stratonovich stochastic differential equation (SDE)

$$d\xi(\mathbf{x}, s) = \mathbf{W}(\xi(\mathbf{x}, s), \circ ds), \quad 0 < s < t, \quad (6)$$

for $\mathbf{w}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \mathbf{W}(\mathbf{x}, dt)$ and for the final-time condition $\xi(\mathbf{x}, t) = \mathbf{x}$ (see Appendix B for more details). By solving (6) for a large number P of points $\mathbf{x}_p, p = 1, \dots, P$ suitably distributed over the domain, one can obtain the discrete representation

$$c(\mathbf{x}_p, t) = c_0(\xi(\mathbf{x}_p, 0)), \quad p = 1, \dots, P. \quad (7)$$

The algorithm was further simplified by DFV using the time-reversibility of the Stratonovich flow³⁴ to write

$$c(\mathbf{x}_p, t) = c_0(\xi(\mathbf{x}_p, t)), \quad p = 1, \dots, P. \quad (8)$$

with (6) now solved forward in time for $0 < s < t$ with $\xi(\mathbf{x}_p, 0) = \mathbf{x}_p$. DFV implemented this strategy by generating velocity realizations \mathbf{w} with a Stokes solver and by using a predictor–corrector scheme to solve the Stratonovich SDE (6) forward in time to evaluate (8). Finally, the Itô and Stratonovich interpretations of (6) are equivalent when $\partial R_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x})/\partial x_j = 0$,³⁴ a condition that easily follows from incompressibility and space-homogeneity. Therefore, in periodic space domains, DFV could solve (6) as an Itô SDE using the Euler–Maruyama method, generating \mathbf{w} by a spectral Stokes solver and using a nonuniform FFT algorithm to sample only the M values $\mathbf{w}(\xi(\mathbf{x}_p, s), s)$ for $p = 1, \dots, P$ required to time-advance the SDE.

It may be useful to explain briefly how the DFV theory fits into the hierarchy of models and methods developed to describe liquid diffusion. This model is best understood as a simplification of full nonlinear Landau–Lifshitz fluctuating hydrodynamics for a binary liquid mixture.³⁵ DFV assumed (i) zero mean velocity, (ii) isothermal conditions, (iii) constant bare diffusivity D_0 at the scale σ of the solute molecule radius and, most importantly, (iv) a very large Schmidt number $\nu/D_0 \gg 1$. In this asymptotic limit and with their other assumptions, DFV derived the Stratonovich stochastic equation (2) for the concentration field or, equivalently, the Itô equation²¹

$$\partial_t c = -\mathbf{w} \cdot \nabla c + \nabla \cdot ((\mathbf{D} + D_0 \mathbf{I}) \nabla c), \quad (9)$$

where $\mathbf{D}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x})$ is a new effective or renormalized diffusivity induced by thermal velocity fluctuations. A notable success of the DFV approach is that it naturally explains observed features of high-Schmidt diffusion, such as the Stokes–Einstein relation for the diffusivity³⁶ and domain size-dependence of the diffusivity in molecular-dynamics studies.³⁷ On the other hand, the assumptions and asymptotic limit in the DFV theory lead to simplified results that miss some common features of real liquid solutions, such as concentration dependence of diffusivity. In principle, the renormalization group³⁸ is a more general method to obtain similar results, without the restriction to high-Schmidt numbers. The DFV theory thus cannot account for some experimental features, such as nonlinear mean profiles arising from the concentration dependence of diffusivity.^{12,39,40} On the other hand, it is a realistic model for isothermal conditions in a fluid at rest and when concentration dependencies can be neglected, e.g., for relatively weak concentration gradients.

III. NEW APPROACHES

Unlike DFV, we aim in this study not to calculate full realizations of the concentration field c but instead to calculate only its statistical cumulants, in particular those of second order. Note that in a space-homogeneous steady-state, e.g., with constant mean gradients, the concentration structure function S is obtained from the second cumulant $C_2(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}') = C_2(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')$ by Fourier transform,

$$S(\mathbf{k}, t) = \int C_2(\mathbf{r}, t) e^{i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r}} d^3 r. \quad (10)$$

Two methods originating in the theory of turbulent advection are especially efficient for computing the cumulants. Both methods apply most directly in physical space.

A. Solution of closed Eulerian equations for second-cumulant

A very useful, well-known feature of the Kraichnan model is that there is no *closure problem*.^{22,23} In particular, cumulants of the concentration field of all orders satisfy exact closed equations. For instance, the first cumulant, or the mean concentration field, $C_1(\mathbf{x}, t) = \langle c(\mathbf{x}, t) \rangle := \bar{c}(\mathbf{x}, t)$, satisfies the diffusion equation with a renormalized diffusivity $\mathbf{D}(\mathbf{x}) = D_0 \mathbf{I} + (1/2) \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x})$,

$$\partial_t \bar{c}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \frac{1}{2} \nabla_{x_i} [R_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}) \nabla_{x_j} \bar{c}(\mathbf{x}, t)] + D_0 \Delta_x \bar{c}(\mathbf{x}, t). \quad (11)$$

The second cumulant, or concentration covariance, $C_2(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, t) := \langle c(\mathbf{x}_1, t) c(\mathbf{x}_2, t) \rangle - \langle c(\mathbf{x}_1, t) \rangle \langle c(\mathbf{x}_2, t) \rangle$, likewise satisfies a multivariate diffusion equation

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t C_2(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, t) = & D_0 \sum_{n=1}^2 \Delta_{\mathbf{x}_n} C_2(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, t) \\ & + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n,m=1}^2 \nabla_{x_n} [R_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_n, \mathbf{x}_m) \nabla_{x_j} C_2(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, t)] \\ & + R_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2) \nabla_{x_1} \bar{c}(\mathbf{x}_1, t) \nabla_{x_2} \bar{c}(\mathbf{x}_2, t), \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

with a source term arising from the mean concentration gradient. This pattern repeats for all higher orders, each cumulant satisfying a multivariate diffusion equation with a source determined by lower-order cumulants.

In this study, we focus on the free diffusion in an unbounded three-dimensional space. For the initial mean concentration profile (1), Eq. (11) reduces to the 1D diffusion equation

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \bar{c}(z, t) = D \partial_z^2 \bar{c}(z, t), \quad (13)$$

where $D = k_B T / 6\pi\eta\sigma$ (for $D_0 \ll D$), with an exact solution

$$\bar{c}(z, t) = \frac{c_0}{2} \left(1 + \operatorname{erf} \left(\frac{z}{2\sqrt{D(t+\tau)}} \right) \right). \quad (14)$$

See standard Ref. 41. Equation (12) for the 2nd-order cumulant can also be simplified by introducing relative and mean variables

$$\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2 = (x, y, z), \quad \mathbf{X} = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{x}_1 + \mathbf{x}_2) = (X, Y, Z),$$

because the velocity statistics are spatially homogeneous and isotropic and, therefore, \mathbf{R} coincides with the Oseen tensor,

$$R_{ij}(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{k_B T}{4\pi\eta r} \left(\delta_{ij} + \frac{r_i r_j}{r^2} \right) \quad \text{if } r \gg \sigma. \quad (15)$$

The second-cumulant C_2 then depends only upon \mathbf{r} and Z and must furthermore be independent of azimuthal angle ϕ in spherical coordinates (r, θ, ϕ) . In those variables, Eq. (12) becomes, for $r \gtrsim \sigma$,

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t C_2 = & \frac{k_B T}{4\pi\eta\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{3} + \frac{\sigma}{4r} (1 + \cos^2 \theta) \right) \partial_Z^2 C_2 \\ & + \frac{k_B T}{3\pi\eta\sigma} \cdot \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left[r^2 \left(1 - \frac{3\sigma}{2r} \right) \frac{\partial C_2}{\partial r} \right] \\ & + \frac{k_B T}{3\pi\eta\sigma} \cdot \frac{1}{r^2 \sin \theta} \left(1 - \frac{3\sigma}{4r} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\sin \theta \frac{\partial C_2}{\partial \theta} \right) \\ & + \frac{k_B T}{4\pi\eta} \cdot \frac{1}{r} (1 + \cos^2 \theta) \nabla \bar{c} \left(Z + \frac{z}{2} \right) \nabla \bar{c} \left(Z - \frac{z}{2} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where $r = (x^2 + y^2 + z^2)^{1/2}$ and $z = r \cos \theta$.

Equation (16) for the second cumulant was the basis for the previous calculation of C_2 near the mid-plane in the long-time, quasi-steady regime,²⁹

$$\begin{aligned} C_2(r, \theta, Z, t) \simeq C^2(t) - \frac{3}{16} \sigma |\nabla \bar{c}(t)|^2 r (2 + \sin^2 \theta), \\ Dt \gg \sigma^2, \quad r \gtrsim \sigma, \quad Z \simeq 0. \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

The concentration variance $\mathcal{C}(t) = C_2(\mathbf{0}, t)$ cannot be determined from Eq. (16), which is only valid for $r \gtrsim \sigma$, and its derivation would require a regularized version of the equation valid for all r (e.g., see Ref. 30, Appendix D). By explicit evaluation of the Fourier transform (10), the physical-space result (17) can be shown²⁹ to be equivalent to the standard expression for the concentration structure function of GCFs in free diffusion, $S(\mathbf{k}, t) \sim \frac{k_B T}{D\eta} |\nabla \bar{c}(t)|^2 |\hat{\mathbf{k}}_\perp|^2 k^{-4}$, where $\hat{\mathbf{k}}_\perp$ is the component of $\hat{\mathbf{k}} = \mathbf{k}/|\mathbf{k}|$ perpendicular to $\hat{\mathbf{z}}$, originally obtained from linearized fluctuating hydrodynamics.¹³

In this study, we derive from (16) a new physical-space expression for the second cumulant in a complementary short-time, large- r regime. Writing the source term in (16) for the mean concentration (14) explicitly as

$$\begin{aligned} S(r, \theta, Z, t) = \frac{k_B T}{4\pi\eta} \cdot \frac{1}{r} (1 + \cos^2 \theta) \frac{c_0^2}{4\pi D(t + \tau)} \times \exp \left[-\frac{Z^2 + \frac{1}{4}z^2}{2D(t + \tau)} \right], \\ r \gtrsim \sigma, \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

the key idea is to take this source as the leading-order contribution to the right-hand side of (16) and treat the diffusion term as a small perturbation. By direct time-integration of the source term (18), one then obtains

$$\begin{aligned} C_2(r, \theta, Z, t) \simeq \frac{3c_0^2}{8\pi} \cdot \frac{\sigma}{r} (1 + \cos^2 \theta) \\ \times \left[E_1 \left(\frac{Z^2 + \frac{1}{4}z^2}{2D(t + \tau)} \right) - E_1 \left(\frac{Z^2 + \frac{1}{4}z^2}{2D\tau} \right) \right], \\ Dt \lesssim \sigma^2 \ll r^2, \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

where $E_1(x)$ is the exponential integral function [see Ref. 42 (Sec. 6.2.1)]. For more details of the derivation, see Appendix A, where it is also shown that the result (19) is just the first term in an asymptotic series for large r .

Note that the expression (19) is valid for all Z . Restricting (19) to the special case $Z^2 + \frac{1}{4}z^2 = 0$, however, the term in square brackets reduces to $\ln(1 + t/\tau)$ and $\simeq t/\tau$ for $t \ll \tau$. In fact, one can see more generally by using the relation $|\nabla c_0|^2 = c_0^2/4\pi D\tau$ that

$$\begin{aligned} C_2(r, \theta, Z = 0, t) \simeq \frac{k_B T}{4\pi\eta} \cdot t \frac{|\nabla c_0|^2}{r} (1 + \cos^2 \theta), \\ Dt \lesssim \sigma^2 \ll r^2 \ll D\tau, \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

where one can see by standard theorems on the asymptotics of Fourier transforms (see Ref. 43, Chap. IX.6, Theorem 4) that this physical-space result corresponds to the spectral structure function

$$\begin{aligned} S(\mathbf{k}, t) \simeq \frac{2k_B T}{\eta} \cdot t |\nabla c_0|^2 \frac{\sin^2 \theta_k}{k^2}, \\ Dt \lesssim \sigma^2, \quad k\sigma \ll 1 \ll Dk^2 \tau, \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

where $\sin \theta_k = |\hat{\mathbf{k}}_\perp|$ is the sine of the angle between \mathbf{k} and $\hat{\mathbf{z}}$ (see Appendix A for details). Equation (21) is exactly the result obtained by DFV,²¹ Sec. III A. In fact, DFV derived their result from a spectral version of our Eq. (12) (see Ref. 44, Sec. 2.1 for the equivalence), with no mean gradient but with instead a non-vanishing spectrum at wavenumber \mathbf{k}_0 so that $\nabla c_0 \simeq c_0 \mathbf{k}_0$. The DFV derivation made transparent the analogy of structure-function growth with a turbulent cascade. In addition, DFV observed this short-time regime clearly in their numerical results for the structure function (see Ref. 21, Fig. 3). It is worth noting that, to our knowledge, the short-time regime with a k^{-2} power-law of the structure function predicted by DFV has not yet been observed experimentally. Our results presented below will shed some light on the requirements to do so.

B. Lagrangian Monte Carlo evaluation of second-cumulant

We exploit here, as well, a Lagrangian numerical scheme similar to that of DFV, but an even earlier version that was developed to calculate statistical correlation functions of a passive scalar advected by the Kraichnan model velocity field.⁴⁵⁻⁴⁷ To calculate the P th moment function $\langle c(\mathbf{x}_1, t) \cdots c(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \rangle$, we use Eq. (8) to evaluate $c(\mathbf{x}_p, t) = c_0(\xi_p(t))$. Therefore, we evolve P stochastic Lagrangian tracers, $\xi_p(t) = \xi(\mathbf{x}_p, t)$, $p = 1, \dots, P$, through a vector of correlated Brownian processes, $\mathbf{W}_P(t) = (\mathbf{w}_1(t), \dots, \mathbf{w}_P(t))$, such that $\mathbf{w}_p(t) = \mathbf{w}(\xi_p, t)$. This is implemented with an Euler-Maruyama discretization

$$\xi_p(t + \Delta t) = \xi_p(t) + \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_p \sqrt{\Delta t}, \quad (22)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{W}}_P = (\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_1, \dots, \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_P)$ is a normal random variable having mean zero and $Pd \times Pd$ covariance matrix

$$R_{pi,qj} = R_{ij}(\xi_p(t), \xi_q(t)), \quad (23)$$

for $p, q = 1, \dots, P$ and $i, j = 1, \dots, d$ in d space dimensions. The main difference from the algorithm of DFV is that P is now a small integer ($P = 2$ for the second cumulant). Therefore, rather than a

non-uniform FFT, we can generate independent samples of the Pd -random vector by writing it as $\tilde{\mathcal{W}}_p = \mathbf{L}_p \tilde{\mathbf{N}}_p$, where \mathbf{L}_p is the lower triangular Cholesky factor of the positive-definite covariance matrix (23) and $\tilde{\mathbf{N}}_p$ is a Pd -dimensional standard normal vector.

As in the earlier study on turbulent advection,^{45–47} the ensemble average that defines the second cumulant is approximated by an empirical average

$$C_2(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, t) \simeq \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N c^{(n)}(\mathbf{x}_1, t) c^{(n)}(\mathbf{x}_2, t), \quad (24)$$

over a large number N of samples, where the concentration fluctuation field is defined by $c^{(n)}(\mathbf{x}_p, t) = c_0(\xi_p^{(n)}(t)) - \bar{c}(\mathbf{x}_p, t)$ and $\xi_p^{(n)}(t)$, $n = 1, \dots, N$ are independent solutions of (6) approximated by the Euler–Maruyama scheme (22). The convergence of the sample average (24) as $N \rightarrow \infty$ is slow, with typical Monte Carlo errors $\propto 1/\sqrt{N}$. Nevertheless, the scheme yielded accurate results for turbulent advection^{45–47} with a number of samples at most $N \sim 10^7$. Unfortunately, our problem differs in two crucial respects. First, the covariance for the Kraichnan model of a turbulent velocity field had covariance increasing with r , whereas the velocity covariance (15) corresponding to thermal noise decreases with r . Formally, the thermal velocity field has Hölder exponent $-1/2$, whereas turbulent velocity fields have positive Hölder exponents. The consequence is that the elements in the $Pd \times Pd$ matrix (23) off-diagonal in p, q , which are entirely responsible for producing correlations between particles, grow smaller in time as particles separate. The second key difference is that the turbulence studies^{45–47} considered a statistical steady-state for the passive scalar with large-scale injection, whereas we study the problem of free diffusion for which the concentration correlations decay in time. This decaying magnitude makes it more

difficult to achieve an acceptable relative error. Both of these differences require that N must be very much larger in our problem. Fortunately, the calculation of the sample average (24) is trivially parallelizable, with only the requirement to choose independent seeds for pseudorandom number generators on different processors. We have developed and applied a parallel GPU code capable of yielding up to $N \sim 10^{15}$ independent samples, whose results we present below. See Appendix B for a full discussion of the numerical methods and their implementation.

As an illustration of our numerical approach, we plot in Fig. 1 a single pair of Lagrangian particles undergoing correlated Brownian motion according to the covariance (23) that is used to calculate one term in the sum (24) for the second cumulant. These and all quantities have been computed in dimensionless units with σ , c_0 , and $\sigma^2/(2D)$ reference scales for length, concentration, and time, respectively. In physical units, by considering, for instance, a dispersion of 10 nm-sized particles in water at ambient conditions, corresponding to $D = 2.2 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$, the reference time is $2.3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ s}$. Non-dimensional variables are hereafter indicated by an asterisk (*) superscript.

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

We here present and discuss our numerical results for the first- and second-order cumulants of the concentration fluctuations in the free diffusion of an initial mean concentration profile (1) that corresponds to a planar interface, either sharp on the molecular scale ($\tau = 0$) or smoothed ($\tau > 0$). Our numerical experiment is closely analogous to several laboratory experiments^{8,11,12} on free diffusion with similar initial concentration profiles. Important differences between these studies and ours are that their spatial domain was finite, and gravity acted in a direction perpendicular to the initial interface. Domain size and buoyancy effects of gravity are both known to quench the concentration fluctuations at large scales.¹³ One experiment¹¹ created an interface by injecting a concentrated solution into water and waiting for gravity to flatten out large-scale fluctuations: this technique is therefore unable to study short-time phenomena. A similar, more recent experiment¹² instead maintains the sharp interface by continuously injecting fluid and sucking it out through a thin slit at the interface. The final experiment⁸ began with a flat interface in two immiscible fluids just below their consolute temperature and then rapidly raised the temperature above that point so that the two fluids could freely mix. The latter two experiments, in principle, might measure short-time fluctuations like those derived by DFV and in Sec. III A.

A. First order cumulant

As a first simple check of our algorithm, we have computed the time development of the mean concentration field for the initial profile of the sharp step function given by Eq. (1) with $\tau = 0$. We use an N -sample average analogous to (24),

$$\bar{c}(\mathbf{x}, t) \simeq \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N c^{(n)}(\mathbf{x}, t), \quad (25)$$

where now $c^{(n)}(\mathbf{x}, t) = c_0(\xi^{(n)}(t))$ and $\xi^{(n)}(0) = \mathbf{x}$ for each $n = 1, \dots, N$. The results presented in Fig. 2 show excellent agreement with the exact solution of the diffusion equation. The plots

FIG. 1. Trajectories of two Lagrangian tracers ending at the positions $\mathbf{x}_1^* = (0, 0, 0)$ and $\mathbf{x}_2^* = (1000, 0, 0)$, indicated by the blue and yellow large circles, respectively. The top panel is limited to intermediate times, $t^* \leq 10^3$, while the bottom one extends up to long times, $t^* \leq 10^9$.

FIG. 2. First order cumulant, i.e., the mean concentration, vs the distance from the initially sharp ($\tau^* = 0$) interface at different times. Symbols represent the numerical results obtained with 10^9 samples, while dashed red lines show the analytical solution (14). Monte Carlo error bars are not visible at the scale of the plot.

in Fig. 2 with $t^* \rightarrow \tau^*$ also represent the smoothed initial data (14) with $\tau^* > 0$.

B. Second order cumulant: Short-time behavior

We next present numerical results for the second cumulant of the concentration fluctuations calculated from (25), first in the

short-time, large- r regime and in the plane of the initial interface for $Z = 0$, in order to check the prediction (20). We further took $\theta = \pi/2$ so that also $z = 0$ and, therefore, the restriction $r^{*2} \ll \tau^*$ in (20) becomes moot. Finally, we chose $\tau^* = 10^4$ so that the approximation should be valid for $t^* \lesssim 1$ and $r^* \gg 1$. The numerical results in Fig. 3 were obtained with a number of samples $N \sim 1.4 \times 10^{13}$, and the error bars from the Monte Carlo error are smaller than the symbol size to plot the data. The numerical values of the cumulant plotted in Fig. 3(b) vs $r^* \in [2, 10^4]$ for various times $t^* \in [0, 1]$ are in remarkably good agreement with the prediction (20). The same results plotted in Fig. 3(a) vs $t^* \in [0, 1]$ for various $r^* \in [2, 10^4]$ only show a moderate difference in growth for the smallest value $r^* = 2$. Therefore, the large- r asymptotic result (20) agrees with the numerical results down to radial distances as small as $r^* = 5$.

As previously discussed, the physical-space result (20) is equivalent to the prediction (21) of DFV for the spectral structure function. However, our more general short-time, large- r result (19) also applies outside of the mid-plane $Z = 0$. To test this more general prediction, we plot in Fig. 4 numerical results for $Z^* = r^* \sqrt{3}/4$ and $\theta = \pi/6$, obtained with numbers of samples $N \sim 2.8 \times 10^{13}$ and Monte Carlo error bars too small to be observed. The prediction (19) should hold for $t^* \lesssim 1$ and $r^* \gg 1$, so that we plot in Fig. 4(b) the cumulant values vs $r^* \in [2, 10^3]$ for various times $t^* \in [0, 1]$. These are again in remarkably good agreement with the prediction (19). The same results plotted in Fig. 4(a) vs $t^* \in [0, 1]$ for various $r^* \in [10, 10^3]$ show a slight difference in growth only for the smallest value, $r^* = 10$, but otherwise agree with the asymptotic prediction (19). To our knowledge, none of these short-time results have yet been observed in laboratory experiments. To address this issue, we next consider the duration of this short-time regime.

FIG. 3. Second order cumulant in the early time regime for points lying on the interface ($Z^* = 0, z^* = 0, \theta = \pi/2$, and $\tau^* = 10^4$). Left: $C_2^* \text{ vs } t^*$. Right: $C_2^* \text{ vs } r^*$. Different symbols refer to different values of r^* and t^* in the left and right panels, respectively. Dashed lines represent the analytical prediction in (20). The number of samples is $\sim 1.4 \times 10^{13}$. The error bars are not visible at the scales of the plots. Times on the upper axis in all plots are for the reference values $\sigma = 10 \text{ nm}$ and $D = 2.2 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$.

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FIG. 4. Second order cumulant in the early time regime for points lying outside of the interface ($Z^* = r^* \cos(\theta)/2$, $z^* = r^* \cos(\theta)$, $\theta = \pi/6$, and $\tau^* = 10^4$). Left: C_2^* vs t^* , with different plots and symbols for different values of r^* . Right: C_2^* vs r^* , with different symbols for different times. Dashed lines represent the analytical prediction in (19). The number of samples is $\sim 2.8 \times 10^{13}$, and the error bars are not visible at the scale of the plots.

C. Second order cumulant: Long-time behavior

A very interesting question is how the long-time quasi-steady regime (17), observed in laboratory experiments on free diffusion,^{8,11} emerges from the early time growth regime discussed in Sec. IV B. Note that the early time prediction was obtained by expanding in t/τ , and its existence depends upon the assumption of an initial graded interface with $\tau > 0$. Furthermore, the theoretical derivation²⁹ of the quasi-steady prediction (17) did not derive the time-dependence of the concentration variance $C^2(t)$. We address here these fundamental issues, not yet answered theoretically, with our numerical Monte Carlo results. For the case $\tau^* = 10^2$, Fig. 5(a) plots the concentration second cumulants obtained with a number of samples $N = 1.5 \times 10^{13}$ for four values of $r^* = 100, 250, 500, 1000$ for a longer range of times $t^* \in [0, 10^5]$. The cumulant values initially rise linearly, as predicted, but then achieve a maximum value and subsequently decay slowly at long times. We note that this maximum value at intermediate times corresponds to the largest experimental signal and may be accessible to laboratory measurement. To better determine the long-time behavior, we plot these results on a much longer time-interval $t^* \in [10^{-1}, 10^9]$ with a log-scale and including additional values $r^* = 5000, 10\,000$ in Fig. 5(b). The early time growth indicated by the dotted line is confirmed to be $\propto t^*$, as expected, and furthermore, the late-time decay indicated by the dashed line is observed to be $\propto (t^*)^{-1/2}$. Note that the short-time regime holds in Fig. 5(b) only for $t^* \lesssim 1000$ which, for a choice of parameters $\sigma = 10$ nm and $D = 2.2 \times 10^{-11}$ m²/s, typical for macromolecules, colloids, or nanoparticles in water, would give $t \lesssim 1$ ms. We have not encountered measurements reported for such short

times. We also plot in this figure the corresponding results for the case of an initial concentration interface that is sharp on the molecular scale, with $\tau = 0$. This case lacks the early time linear growth regime, but its late-time behavior coincides with that for $\tau > 0$. For simplicity, we hereafter consider the late-time regime mainly for the case $\tau = 0$.

Since the term $\propto r$ in the quasi-steady prediction (17) decays in time at the faster rate $|\nabla c(z = 0, t)|^2 \propto 1/t$, we can thus identify the origin of the slow decay with $C^2(t) \propto t^{-1/2}$. This power law can be explained if one postulates a long-time self-similar decay, at least in the central plane perpendicular to the gradient,

$$C_2\left(r, \theta = \frac{\pi}{2}, Z = 0, t\right) \sim C^2(t)F(r/L(t)). \quad (26)$$

Adopting the reasonable hypothesis that $L(t) \propto (Dt)^{1/2}$, then (17) can be consistent with the self-similar ansatz (26) only if $C^2(t) \propto c_0^2 \sigma / (Dt)^{1/2}$.

The numerical results for the scaling function $F(\rho) := C_2(r, \theta = \pi/2, Z = 0, t) / C^2(t)$ as a function of $\rho = r/L(t)$ with $\tau = 0$ are plotted in Fig. 6 for five different values of r^* . The very good collapse of the results for the different values of r^* supports (and indeed originally suggested) the hypothesis of asymptotic self-similarity as in (26). We observe in Fig. 6(a) for the range $\rho < 1$ a linear behavior of $F(\rho)$, with the best fit indicated by the dashed line, that corresponds to the experimentally observed “giant concentration fluctuations” with the structure function $\propto k^{-4}$. Interestingly, Fig. 6(b) for the range $\rho \gg 1$ with a log-scale shows instead an asymptotic

FIG. 5. Second order cumulant vs time (full timescale) for points lying on the interface ($Z^* = 0, z^* = 0, \theta = \pi/2$). Different symbols represent different values of r^* in both panels. (Left) From early to intermediate times with an initially smooth interface ($\tau^* = 10^2$). (Right) Superposition of results from initially sharp ($\tau^* = 0$) and initially smooth interfaces ($\tau^* = 10^2$) in solid and translucent lines with symbols, respectively. Power laws are also reported in black dashed lines. Data are obtained by averaging over 1.5×10^{13} samples, and the error bars are too small to be observed at this scale.

FIG. 6. Self-similarity of the second order cumulant for points lying on the initially sharp interface ($Z^* = 0, z^* = 0, \theta = \pi/2, \tau^* = 0$). The scaling function $F(\rho) = C_2(r^*, t^*)/C_2^2(t^*)$ is shown vs ρ with different symbols for different values of r^* . The black dashed line is a linear fit for $\rho \leq 1$, and the red dotted-dashed line is the fit of a $\propto 1/\rho$ function for $\rho > 1$. The number of samples is 1.5×10^{13} . For the sake of clarity, error bars are omitted here; however, they do not alter the scaling law.

behavior $\propto 1/\rho$, with the best fit indicated by the dashed-dotted line. To our knowledge, this quasi-steady regime, which would correspond to a structure function $\propto k^{-2}$ at very low wavenumbers, has never been observed experimentally, presumably due to domain-size

effects. Note that this scaling at large ρ implies that the self-similar solution $C_2(r, t)$ in (26) should become independent of t for short times. This independence is observed clearly in the sharp-gradient case $\tau = 0$. In this case, self-similarity is valid immediately for all $t > 0$, because the initial data impose no characteristic length scale, which must then be “forgotten” in the subsequent evolution.

The appearance of self-similar behavior at long times should not be unexpected, since it is typical in turbulent decay processes. To demonstrate it analytically, one could follow standard approaches for turbulently advected passive scalars.⁴⁴ There are, however, two important differences in the present case compared with turbulent scalars. First, the model fields for a turbulent velocity are chosen to have spatial Hölder exponent h in the range $0 < h < 1$, whereas the thermal velocity field with spatial covariance given by the Oseen tensor (15) has negative Hölder exponent $-1/2$. The resulting Eq. (12) for C_2 thus is more similar to the equation for the correlation function of a turbulently advected magnetic field, where the stretching term in the magnetic induction equation involves the velocity gradient with negative Hölder exponent $h - 1$. Self-similar decay solutions have been studied⁴⁸ for the magnetic correlation function in the non-dynamo regime of the Kraichnan–Kazantsev model, but this required including a resistive regularization and using a matched asymptotic expansion to patch together solutions at the inertial scale and at the resistive scale. Similarly, in our problem, a regularization of Eq. (16) at scales $r < \sigma$ (e.g., see Ref. 30, Appendix D) must be introduced, and matched solutions at those scales and at $r > \sigma$ must be developed. The second additional difficulty in the current problem is that statistics are spatially inhomogeneous and anisotropic. This problem may be addressed by considering a partially integrated correlation function

$$\bar{C}_2(r, t) := \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dZ \int_0^\pi \sin \theta d\theta C_2(r, \theta, Z, t), \quad (27)$$

which is now homogeneous and isotropic, and which satisfies a simplified equation

$$\partial_t \bar{C}_2 = \frac{k_B T}{3\pi\eta\sigma} \cdot \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left[r^2 \left(1 - \frac{3\sigma}{2r} \right) \frac{\partial \bar{C}_2}{\partial r} \right] + \bar{S}(r, t), \quad (28)$$

where \bar{S} is obtained by similarly integrating the source term S in Eq. (18),

$$\bar{S}(r, t) = \frac{k_B T}{4\pi\eta} \cdot \frac{c_0^2}{r^2} \left[\left(1 + \frac{4D(t+\tau)}{r^2} \right) \operatorname{erf} \left(\frac{r}{\sqrt{8D(t+\tau)}} \right) - \frac{(2D(t+\tau))^{1/2}}{r} \exp \left(\frac{-r^2}{8D(t+\tau)} \right) \right]. \quad (29)$$

As in the quasi-steady regime,²⁹ solving this equation can be the first step to obtaining the full solution in the asymptotic self-similar regime. We hope to pursue this problem in future studies.

Returning to the numerical results, we confirm in detail the quasi-stationary prediction (17) at long times and at length scales $\sigma \ll r \ll L(t)$. In Fig. 7, we plot our numerical results for the second cumulant vs r^* for very long times. We see in Fig. 7(a) that the quasi-steady predictions hold well for $t^* \gtrsim 10^7$ over a growing range of lengths r^* , as expected. Note that the linear fits have intercepts determined by the empirical decay law for $C^2(t)$, but the slopes are given analytically by the predicted quasi-stationary formula (17). To emphasize the quality of the fit at long times, we plot in Fig. 7(b) the numerical results for four times $t^* > 10^8$ over the range $r^* \in [0, 10^4]$, where one can see that the linear scaling with the predicted slope matches the data very well.

Finally, we study the very fundamental issue of the emergence of the long-range correlations and the approach to the asymptotic

self-similar behavior at long times. In order to provide an initial regime before self-similarity develops, we consider the case $\tau > 0$ and plot in Fig. 8 the results for $F(\rho, t/\tau) := C_2(r, \theta = \pi/2, Z = 0, t)/C^2(t)$ vs $\rho = r/L(t)$ at six values of the dimensionless time $t/\tau = t^*/\tau^*$. For comparison, we also plot the fit for the asymptotic scaling function $F(\rho)$ determined from Fig. 6. As expected from our short-time, large- r asymptotic analysis, the tail $F(\rho) \sim 0.12/\rho$ at $\rho \gtrsim 1$ is confirmed in Fig. 6(b) to be approached from below by a similar $1/\rho$ -tail with amplitude initially growing linearly in t/τ . Very interestingly, the emergence of the standard quasi-stationary regime with linear behavior $F(\rho) \sim 0.19 - 0.08\rho$ for $\rho \lesssim 1$ is observed in Fig. 6(a) to emerge in a similar manner, so that the results $F(\rho, t/\tau)$ are described well by affine functions with negative slopes $\sim t/\tau$ at early times. To our knowledge, this emergence of the asymptotic quasi-steady behavior has not been observed previously, either by simulation or by experiment.

Observations from light-scattering experiments are naturally couched in terms of the spectral structure functions. We cannot take the Fourier transform (10) of our available numerical results in physical space, because we have data for only the two angles $\theta = \pi/2, \pi/6$ presented. We can infer from standard mathematical asymptotic results⁴³ that $S(\mathbf{k}, t) \propto k^{-4}$ for $kL(t) \gtrsim 1$ and $\propto k^{-2}$ for $kL(t) \lesssim 1$, but without a prediction of the angular dependence. Our results can be compared with experimental observations of Carpineti *et al.*¹⁹ and especially of Cerbino *et al.*,¹⁸ who both studied a slightly different problem: the growth of long-range non-equilibrium concentration correlations in a transient thermodiffusion process rather than in free diffusion. Both experiments began in a constant concentration state and then suddenly imposed a temperature gradient, leading to a developing concentration gradient by the Soret effect. A low-gravity experiment and numerical simulations in the first of these papers¹⁸ observed a self-similar growth of the Fourier

FIG. 7. Long-time regime of the second order cumulant vs the separation r^* for points lying on the interface ($Z^* = 0, z^* = 0, \theta = \pi/2$, and $\tau^* = 0$). Different solid lines represent different times, with symbols shown only for $\rho \leq 1$. Dashed lines show the expected linear behavior with the given slope (17) and fitted variance. Left: From intermediate to long times. Right: Enlargement over long times. Data are obtained with 1.5×10^{13} samples, and error bars are shown by the shaded bend around solid lines (best visible in the right panel).

FIG. 8. Dynamical development of the self-similar second order cumulant for points lying on an initially smooth interface ($Z^* = 0, z^* = 0, \theta = \pi/2$, and $\tau^* > 0$). The scaling function $F(\rho) = C_2(r^*, t^*) / C^2(t^*)$ is shown vs ρ with different symbols now representing different normalized times, t^*/τ^* . The black dashed and the red dotted-dashed lines are taken from Fig. 6 and represent the expected behaviors for $t^*/\tau^* \rightarrow \infty$ when $\rho < 1$ and $\rho > 1$, respectively. The number of samples varies for each point shown, with the most demanding conditions (large ρ) requiring 1.5×10^{13} realizations. All results are obtained by varying τ^* , t^* , and r^* while guaranteeing that $r^* \geq 50$. Colored bands show the Monte Carlo error.

structure function, analogous to what we find in Fig. 6 for the spatial correlation function. Furthermore, the characteristic length-scale to collapse their data at different times was $L(t) = (Dt)^{1/2}$, exactly the same as ours (see their Fig. 6).¹⁸ Their numerical data matched well the predictions of linearized fluctuating hydrodynamics with realistic boundary conditions,⁴⁹ which yield a k^{-4} structure function at $k \gg 1/L_{dom}$, with L_{dom} the domain size. In fact, the numerical model¹⁸ was the fluctuating hydrodynamics of a binary mixture in an overdamped limit for a high Schmidt number, very close to the DFV model.

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The main contribution of this study has been to investigate the DFV model²¹ of high-Schmidt mixing using tools borrowed from turbulence theory. First, we have exploited the existence of a closed hierarchy of dynamical equations for cumulants of all orders, which may, in principle, be solved iteratively. Extending the short-time approximation of DFV to large spatial distances, we have obtained an exact asymptotic form for the second cumulant of concentration fluctuations in physical space. In particular, our formula extends the result of DFV to points outside the mid-plane at $Z = 0$. We have furthermore applied to the DFV model a Lagrangian Monte Carlo numerical method to calculate the cumulants. This approach verifies the predictions of DFV and our own for the short-time, large- r regime. In addition, and apparently for the first time, we have observed numerically in the DFV model the standard long-time quasi-stationary regime in free diffusion from an initial

mean profile, with non-equilibrium long-range correlations $\propto r$ for $r \lesssim L(t)$, where $L(t) = (2Dt)^{1/2}$. More importantly, our numerical study has discovered a new quasi-steady regime at scales $r \gtrsim L(t)$ with decaying correlation of concentration fluctuations $\sim 1/r$. Furthermore, the two ranges for $r \lesssim L(t)$ and for $r \gtrsim L(t)$ appear together in an asymptotic self-similar decay solution. Finally, we have established exactly how this self-similar form is approached in time, thus answering for high-Schmidt liquid mixing the fundamental question of how non-equilibrium long-range correlations emerge. It would be very illuminating to study this transient process in laboratory experiments in order to determine the accuracy of the model predictions.

We learned much about this subject from conversations with Aleks Donev, who warmly encouraged us to pursue the connection between liquid diffusion and turbulent cascade. Aleks was especially excited about the time-reversibility of the DFV model, fully manifest when taking the bare diffusivity $D_0 = 0$. He was passionate about the vision of high-Schmidt scalar mixing as an effect of advection by thermal velocity fluctuations in detailed balance, going beyond traditional Fickian diffusion, and he believed that this more accurate portrayal offered fundamentally new perspectives into the foundations of hydrodynamics. We are honored to offer this study in memory of Aleks and his great legacy in the study of fluctuating hydrodynamics, colloids, materials science, and computational biology.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We are grateful to many colleagues for discussions of this study, most especially Aleksandar Donev, and including also Roberto Benzi, Luca Biferale, Carlo Massimo Casciola, Mauro Sbragaglia, and Eric Vanden-Eijnden. This study is supported by an ERC grant (ERC-STG E-Nucl. Grant Agreement No. 101163330) (PI M.G.). Support is acknowledged also from the Sapienza Funding Scheme “Avvio alla Ricerca - Tipo 2,” Project No. AR22419078AD8186 (PI M.B.). Computational resources were made available from ICSC-Italian Research Center on High Performance Computing, Big Data, and Quantum Computing under “MDR-TP - Spoke 6.” We also acknowledge support for computational resources from CINECA under the IS CRA initiative, relative to the IS CRA-B D-RESIN (PI M.G.) and IS CRA-C EMADON (PI M.B.) projects. G.L.E. acknowledges the Department of Physics of the University of Rome “Tor Vergata” for hospitality while this study was begun and acknowledges support from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (Grant Agreement No. 882340). *Funded by the European Union.* Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Council Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

Marco Bussoletti: Conceptualization (supporting); Data curation (lead); Formal analysis (lead); Funding acquisition (lead); Investigation (supporting); Methodology (supporting); Resources (lead); Software (lead); Visualization (lead); Writing – original draft (lead); Writing – review & editing (supporting). **Mirko Gallo:** Conceptualization (supporting); Data curation (lead); Funding acquisition (lead); Investigation (supporting); Methodology (supporting); Resources (lead); Software (lead); Visualization (supporting); Writing – review & editing (supporting). **Amir Jafari:** Conceptualization (supporting); Data curation (lead); Formal analysis (supporting); Funding acquisition (lead); Investigation (supporting); Methodology (supporting); Resources (lead); Software (supporting); Visualization (lead); Writing – review & editing (supporting). **Gregory L. Eyink:** Conceptualization (lead); Formal analysis (lead); Investigation (lead); Methodology (lead); Software (supporting); Writing – original draft (lead); Writing – review & editing (supporting).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17358631>.

APPENDIX A: SHORT-TIME, LARGE-DISTANCE ASYMPTOTICS

The zeroth order approximation (19) to the second cumulant at small t and large r is given by the time-integral of the source (18),

$$C_2^{(0)}(r, \theta, Z, t) = \int_0^t S(r, \theta, Z, s) ds. \quad (\text{A1})$$

By the change of variables $u = a/(s + \tau)$,

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^t \exp\left(-\frac{a}{s + \tau}\right) \frac{ds}{s + \tau} &= \int_{a/(t + \tau)}^{a/\tau} e^{-u} \frac{du}{u} \\ &= E_1\left(\frac{a}{t + \tau}\right) - E_1\left(\frac{a}{\tau}\right), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A2})$$

where $E_1(x) = \int_x^\infty e^{-u} du/u$ is the exponential integral function [see Ref. 42 (Sec. 6.2.1)]. Using this result to evaluate (A1) yields immediately (19) in the main text. Because $E_1(x) \sim e^{-x}/x$ for $x \rightarrow \infty$ [see Ref. 42 (Sec. 6.12.1)], we have the upper bound $C_2^{(0)} = O\left(\frac{t}{\tau r}\right)$.

This approximation is just the leading term in an asymptotic expansion for small t and large r ,

$$C_2(r, \theta, Z, t) = C_2^{(0)}(r, \theta, Z, t) + C_2^{(1)}(r, \theta, Z, t) + \dots \quad (\text{A3})$$

Substituting (A3) into (16) yields an equation for $C_2^{(1)}$,

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t C_2^{(1)} &= \frac{k_B T}{4\pi\eta\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{3} + \frac{\sigma}{4r} (1 + \cos^2 \theta) \right) \partial_Z^2 C_2^{(0)} \\ &+ \frac{k_B T}{3\pi\eta\sigma} \cdot \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left[r^2 \left(1 - \frac{3\sigma}{2r} \right) \frac{\partial C_2^{(0)}}{\partial r} \right] \\ &+ \frac{k_B T}{3\pi\eta\sigma} \cdot \frac{1}{r^2 \sin \theta} \left(1 - \frac{3\sigma}{4r} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\sin \theta \frac{\partial C_2^{(0)}}{\partial \theta} \right). \end{aligned}$$

The contributions from derivatives ∂_r and ∂_θ straightforwardly give $\partial_t C_2^{(1)} = O\left(\frac{t}{\tau r} \frac{D}{r^2}\right)$. This is less obvious for contributions arising from the derivative ∂_Z , but an explicit computation shows that

$$\begin{aligned} D\partial_Z^2 E_1\left(\frac{Z^2 + \frac{1}{4}z^2}{2D\tau}\right) &= 2D\left(\frac{Z^2}{D\tau} - 1\right) \frac{\exp\left(-\left(Z^2 + \frac{1}{4}z^2\right)/2D\tau\right)}{Z^2 + \frac{1}{4}z^2} \\ &+ 4DZ^2 \frac{\exp\left(-\left(Z^2 + \frac{1}{4}z^2\right)/2D\tau\right)}{\left(Z^2 + \frac{1}{4}z^2\right)^2}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A4})$$

and likewise for $\tau \rightarrow t + \tau$. Since $z = r \cos \theta$, these contributions satisfy the same bound as the others. Hence, integrating in time, $C_2^{(1)} = O\left(\frac{t}{\tau r} \frac{D}{r^2}\right)$. Computation of further terms in the asymptotic expansion (A3) proceeds in the same manner, with the result that $C_2^{(k)} = O\left(\frac{t}{\tau r} \left(\frac{D}{r^2}\right)^k\right)$ for all integers $k \geq 0$.

Using the convergent expansion [see Ref. 42 (Sec. 6.6.2)],

$$E_1(x) = -\gamma - \ln x - \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-x)^k}{k \cdot k!}, \quad (\text{A5})$$

it follows that

$$\lim_{a \rightarrow 0} [E_1(ax) - E_1(a\bar{y})] = \ln(y/x). \quad (\text{A6})$$

For the case $Z^2 + \frac{1}{4}z^2 = 0$, the identity shows that the term in the square bracket of (19) reduces to $\ln(1 + t/\tau)$. Therefore, (A6) yields (20) for the special case $Z = 0, \theta = \pi/2$. More generally, one can derive (20) for $\theta \neq \pi/2$ by considering the time-derivative at $t = 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t C_2(r, \theta, Z = 0, t)|_{t=0} &= S(r, \theta, Z = 0, t = 0) \\ &= \frac{k_B T}{4\pi\eta} \frac{|\nabla c_0|^2}{r} (1 + \cos^2 \theta) \exp\left[-\frac{r^2 \cos^2 \theta}{8D\tau}\right]. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A7})$$

The exponential factor in (A7) is ≈ 1 for $D\tau \gg r^2$ so that (20) then emerges as the first-order Taylor approximation in time.

The Fourier transform of (20) [with our convention in Eq. (10)] can be evaluated from standard asymptotics of Fourier integrals (see Ref. 43, Chap. IX.6, Theorem 4),

$$\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{1}{r} + \frac{z^2}{r^3}\right) \approx (2\pi)^{3/2} \left[\frac{L}{k^2} - L^* \frac{\partial^2}{\partial k_z^2} (\ln k) \right],$$

where \mathcal{F} denotes Fourier transform, while

$$L = 2^{3/2-1} \Gamma\left(\frac{3-1}{2}\right) / \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) = \left(\frac{2}{\pi}\right)^{1/2},$$

and

$$L^* = -1/2^{3/2-1} \Gamma\left(\frac{3}{2}\right) = -\left(\frac{2}{\pi}\right)^{1/2}.$$

Since $\frac{\partial^2}{\partial k_z^2} (\ln k) = \frac{1}{k^2} - \frac{2k_z^2}{k^4}$, we obtain

$$\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{1}{r} + \frac{z^2}{r^3}\right) \approx 8\pi \left(\frac{k^2 - k_z^2}{k^4} \right) = 8\pi \frac{\sin^2 \theta_k}{k^2}.$$

Applying this result to the correlation in (20), we obtain immediately the Fourier structure function (21).

APPENDIX B: MONTE CARLO NUMERICAL SOLVER

The stochastic Lagrangian flow is defined by Eq. (6) in terms of the Brownian vector field,

$$\mathbf{W}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \lambda_n^{-1/2} \phi_n(\mathbf{x}) W_n(t), \quad (\text{B1})$$

where $\phi_n(\mathbf{x})$, $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ are the complete set of orthonormal eigenfunctions of the Stokes operator, $\lambda_n > 0$, $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ are the corresponding eigenvalues, and $W_n(t)$, $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ are a set of i.i.d. standard Brownian motions. The zero-mean, white-noise field $\mathbf{w}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \mathbf{W}(\mathbf{x}, dt)$ thus has the covariance (3), and the flow Eq. (6) can be written in more detail as the Stratonovich stochastic differential equation (SDE)

$$d\xi(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \lambda_n^{-1/2} \phi_n(\xi(\mathbf{x}, t)) \circ \mathbf{W}_n(dt). \quad (\text{B2})$$

Note, however, that converting this equation to Itô form merely adds a drift field $\frac{1}{2} \partial R_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') / \partial x_j|_{\mathbf{x}=\mathbf{x}'}$, which vanishes for the current problem because of the space-homogeneity and incompressibility of the random field $\mathbf{w}(\mathbf{x}, t)$. For this reason, the Lagrangian Monte Carlo algorithm presented in Sec. III can employ the Euler–Maruyama discretization (22), which converges to the Itô SDEs for the p correlated Lagrangian particles obtained by taking $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}_k$, $k = 1, \dots, p$ in (B2). For more background, see standard texts on stochastic flows.³⁴

The Monte Carlo algorithm presented in Sec. III is based on a regularized version of (23) that accounts for the filtering of wavenumbers $\geq 1/\sigma$. Specifically, we implement the exponentially decaying kernel proposed in Ref. 30, Appendix D, which also reproduces the expected Stokes–Einstein macroscopic diffusion $D = k_B T / 6\pi\eta\sigma$ in (13). For the sake of better performance, the numerical solver implements the regularization when $|\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2| \leq 10\sigma$ and (15) otherwise. Moreover, we exploit an adaptive time-stepping method for the Euler–Maruyama time-discretization in (22) such that $\Delta t = (f |\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2|)^2 / 2D$, where $0 < f \leq 1$ is a parameter controlling what fraction of the distance between the two Lagrangian tracers can be covered on average with one time step. We use $f = 0.2$ in our results—tests with smaller and larger fractions confirm that the time scheme is converging.

Although conceptually simple, the Lagrangian Monte Carlo algorithm requires careful implementation to efficiently support an extremely high number of realizations. Given the algorithm's inherently parallel structure, GPU architectures are the natural choice. To this end, we have developed a CUDA + MPI implementation that minimizes communication—the real bottleneck in reduction-heavy algorithms—by hierarchically distributing realizations and reductions across nodes, GPU devices, GPU blocks, warps, and, finally, batches in each thread. The `Philox_4x32_10` (pseudo)random number generator from the `cuRAND` library is used. This implementation allowed us to reach 10^{13} realizations with a computational cost of ~ 7 GPU-hours.

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